

Formation Constants of Cr(III) Complexes with Some Sulphur Containing Ligands

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Proton-ligand formation constants and formation constants of Cr(III) complexes of *p*-(Mercaptoacetamido)-anisole (PMAA), thioglycollanilide (TGA), *p*-(Mercaptoacetamido)-chlorobenzene (PMCB), *m*-(mercaptoacetamido)-phenol (*m*-MAP), and thiosalicylic (TSA) acid have been determined by various computational methods at 30° using 50% (v/v) dioxane-water as a solvent. The stability follows the order:

IN continuation of our earlier work¹⁻⁶ this communication deals with the determination of formation constants of Cr(III) complexes of *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)-anisole (PMAA), thioglycollanilide (TGA), *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)-chlorobenzene (*p*-MCB), *m*-(mercaptoacetamido)-phenol (*m*-MAP), and thiosalicylic (TSA) acid in 50% aqueous dioxane (v/v) media at 30° ± 0.1° and 0.1M (NaClO₄) ionic strength. The approach to the problem was essentially Bjerrum's *p*H-titration technique⁷ as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁸.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either B.D.H. AnalaR or equivalent quality.

*p*H of the solutions was measured using Polymetron CL-41 *p*H meter with an accuracy of ±0.05 *p*H unit.

Corrections for *p*H-measurements in aqueous-dioxane medium were made as described by van Uitert and Haas¹². The change in volume on mixing water and dioxane was determined by measuring the densities of the pure liquids and of the mixture as described by Irving and Rossotti¹³. The concentrations of the reactants were calculated with allowance of this contraction and also for volume changes due to the addition of alkali during the titration.

Experimental setup and the method of calculation is the same as described earlier²⁻⁶.

Results and Discussion

Calculation of stepwise first and second formation constants K_1 and K_2 of the Cr(III) complexes with the aforementioned ligands from the metal-ligand titrations were accomplished by the various computational methods, viz., interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values⁹, successive approximation¹⁰ and linear plot methods. The refined values are obtained by the method of least squares¹¹ and are given in Table 1. Since evaluation of formation constants required a knowledge of the proton-ligand formation constant of the ligand, it was determined under similar experimental conditions and are also recorded in Table 1.

There was no evidence of metal ion hydrolysis, polynuclear complexes, protonated complexes of influence of nitrate, chloride, perchlorate and alkali metal cations. Logarithm values of proton-ligand formation constants of the afore-mentioned ligands and formation constants of corresponding Cr(III) complexes, are given in Table 1. It is quite clear from Table 1 that all the Cr(III) complexes are fairly stable. Since activity co-efficient corrections have been applied, values of proton-ligand formation constants and formation constants reported here are the thermodynamic ones. These constants were reproducible to 0.05 log units or less in replicate determinations, while variation in the initial concentration of metal and chelating agent gave results with a variation of ±0.1 log units or less. The formation curves, drawn by plotting $\bar{n}$ values against $p(L)$ are continuous and do not show flattening at $\bar{n} = 1$. All the formation curves extend upto $\bar{n} \approx 2$ showing the formation of only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 species in solution under the experimental conditions used in the present investigation.

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TABLE 1. FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cr(III) COMPLEXES

Cr(III) = 0.001M; Ligand = 0.01M, NaOH = 0.1M, T = 30° ± 0.1°; Medium, 50% (v/v) dioxane-water.

Ligand	^a log K ₁ ^H	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K _{av}	^b log β ₂	^b log K ₁ /K ₂
<i>p</i> -MAA	9.12(L)	7.20(L)	5.50(L)	6.35(L)	12.70(L)	1.70
	9.17(H)	7.24(H)	5.50(H)			
	9.08(A)	7.18(A)	5.47(A)			
	9.12(P)	7.22(P)	5.50(P)			
TGA	9.02(L)	7.12(L)	5.35(L)	6.23(L)	12.47(L)	1.77
	9.10(H)	7.09(H)	5.30(H)			
	9.00(A)	7.17(A)	5.30(A)			
	9.02(P)	7.10(P)	5.37(P)			
<i>p</i> -MCB	8.90(L)	6.95(L)	5.25(L)	6.10(L)	12.20(L)	1.70
	8.93(H)	7.00(H)	5.25(H)			
	8.96(A)	6.89(A)	5.25(A)			
	8.92(P)	6.90(P)	5.25(P)			
<i>m</i> -MAP	8.80(L)	6.85(L)	5.00(L)	5.92(L)	11.85(L)	1.85
	8.80(H)	6.79(H)	5.05(H)			
	8.80(A)	5.87(A)	5.00(A)			
	8.80(P)	6.90(P)	5.00(P)			
TSA	12.12(3.25)	*6.55(L)	4.85(L)	5.70(L)	11.40(L)	1.70
		6.60(H)	4.90(H)			
		6.55(A)	4.80(A)			
		6.55(P)	4.85(P)			

* Protonation constant for the carboxylic group of TSA.

^aL = Least squares method, H = interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values,

A = successive approximation, P = linear plot method.

^bValues of log K_{av} and log K₁/K₂ have been computed from log K₁ and log K₂ obtained by the method of least squares.

Perusal of Table 1 shows that the stability of Cr(III) complexes follows the order :

In general there is a good correlation between log K_{av} and proton-ligand formation constants of the ligands. A similar relationship is also observed using log K₁ or log K₂ instead of log K_{av}. This suggests that steric effects are of minor importance in determining the stabilities of Cr(III) complexes.

As normally encountered, the average formation constants, log K_{av}, are consistently lower than the logarithm values of proton-ligand formation constant and the ratio log (K₁/K₂) is found to be positive for all the systems. Separation factors between first and second formation constants are well within the expected range and the absence of high values implies that there is little or no steric hindrance to the addition of the second ligand molecule.

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